

The Role of Skills and Work Experience on Employee Performance in PT BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar with Job Satisfaction as Mediating Variable

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ABSTRACT: With job satisfaction as the mediating variable, this study looks at how employee performance at PT BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar is affected by skills and work experience. The sample was determined to be as many as 87 employees, and the analysis method used is Smart PLS 3.9. Regarding Path Coefficients, the findings indicate that Satisfaction affects performance the most, with a value as high as 6,371, while Experience affects performance the least, with a value as low as 2,794. Then, based on Indirect Effect Analysis, due to the p-value being less than 0.05, have found that job satisfaction influences performance through skills. Similarly, Experience affects performance by influencing job satisfaction, and this is also accepted.

KEYWORDS: Work Experience, Employee Performance, Work Skills, Job Satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

A company's operations, whether in the commerce, industrial, or services sector, will constantly aim to accomplish the established objectives. One of the most crucial aspects is that the effectiveness of the activities within it in completing tasks to reach an objective depends not only on the current level of technological proficiency, the infrastructure, and the available facilities but also on the effective use of human resources. The broad management discipline known as human resource management (HRM) encompasses several control, implementation, organization, and planning facets (Rivai, 2013). As globalization progresses, competition among businesses is inevitable; human resources are the most crucial component of a business due to their link with. Employees are the future determinants of a company's ability to reach its goals. Thus, businesses without them will not function at their best (Themba and Amin, 2021).

Since the effectiveness of management is dependent on the caliber of its human resources, human resources present a challenge to business management. The business will continue to function efficiently if its human resources—employees—can do their jobs well. The performance of its personnel determines the longevity of a business. Work skills, work experience, and other criteria are some of the aspects that affect employee effectiveness. Whether a business succeeds or fails in continuing to exist depends on its employees, who keep the business operating as effectively and efficiently as possible (Lengkong, Lengkong, and Taroreh, 2019).

Enhancing performance is the company's aim for properly achieving its objectives. It is hoped that the company's employees' performance will allow it to compete with other businesses. Every person performs differently, which is undoubtedly a significant consideration when assessing employee performance. To gain a competitive edge among the public, businesses must be able to compete with comparable businesses and attempt to improve a product. Enhancing the general caliber of personnel is one way to boost business performance. Every employee must learn and impart knowledge in their respective fields. As a result, each employee must possess the necessary abilities to perform well, particularly in areas of work that call for them (Liana, 2020).

Employee job satisfaction is crucial (Nurcahyani & Adnyani, 2016). Employee reactions to company strategy are influenced by job satisfaction. A business undoubtedly has a relationship with its employees, who are a part of human resources, and employee satisfaction can be determined by their job outcomes. Job satisfaction has an impact on the condition of the workplace as well. If work satisfaction among employees declines, the company's standing will be negatively impacted. The company's productivity level declines as a result of lower employee satisfaction.

Skills are the capacity to perform tasks with ease and caution. Psychomotor actions are typically the focus of this definition. Additionally, skills can be understood as practice-based tasks or as the results of tasks (Zaeni et al., 2021). Furthermore, talent is

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the ability to do various jobs resulting from training and experience (Joseph & Likumahua, 2019). Skills also require fundamental abilities to perform tasks quickly and accurately and the training to build talents.

If they are consistently refined and trained to become experts and master one of the current skill fields, their skills will advance. The company will need and value a skilled worker since, with their abilities, it can accomplish its objectives in line with its targets (Tolo et al., 2016).

Experience, on the other hand, highlights a person's potential. Individuals can learn and develop their behavioral potential through formal and informal education, or experience can be viewed as a process that guides them to a higher pattern of conduct. Learning also involves specific behavioral adjustments brought about by practice, comprehension, and experience.

The length of time a person has worked is a key factor in determining how well he understands and performs his job duties (Jano, Wellem, and Mone, 2023). Experienced workers can work more quickly and readily adjust to the tasks assigned, and they will be better equipped to grasp what to do when a problem emerges.

More attention should be paid to the company's human resources situation so that skilled and experienced workers can be role models. The business will gain from those with expertise and experience.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM STATEMENT

Employee performance issues are not isolated occurrences; various circumstances influence them. According to Karyoto (2016), workers can use their skills to perform specific tasks and deliver the best outcomes. Employees' work experience is crucial to their roles in a firm since they better understand what to do in the event of a conflict.

This study is important because it clarifies how job satisfaction at PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency influences employee performance by mitigating the effects of work experience and skill sets. The study's goals were (1) to examine how PT. Their skill impacted BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency employees' job satisfaction. (2) To examine how work experience affects PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency employees' job satisfaction. (3) To examine how PT. Their skill impacts BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency workers' performance. (4) To examine the impact of skills on PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency workers' performance. (5) To examine how PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency employees' job satisfaction affects their performance. (6) To examine how PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency employees' job satisfaction mediates the impact of skills on their performance. (6) To examine how job satisfaction mediates between work experience and employee performance at PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency.

According to the previously provided explanation, the following is the research's framework:

Image 1. Theoretical Framework

The hypothesis developed according to the framework is as follows:

- H1: Employee job satisfaction at PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency is significantly impacted by skills.
- H2: Employee job satisfaction at PT BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency is significantly impacted by work experience.
- H3: Employee performance at PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency is significantly impacted by skills.
- H4: Employee performance at PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency is significantly impacted by skills.
- H5: The performance of PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency personnel is significantly impacted by job satisfaction.
- H6: At PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency, job satisfaction acts as a mediator between skills and employee performance..
- H7: Job satisfaction at PT. BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency acts as a mediator between work experience and employee performance.

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II. RESEARCH METHODS

This kind of study is quantitative. Due to its bigger sample size and more methodical approach to research from beginning to end, quantitative research has a more complex degree of variation (Sahir, 2021).

According to Sugiyono (2018), Before conclusions are drawn, researchers analyze a population, a category for generalization composed of objects or people with particular characteristics. One hundred twelve employees in the demographic became the focus of this study.

PT's employees were sampled, even though the sample reflects the population's size and characteristics. There are up to 87 workers at BPR Bank Daerah Karanganyar Regency. The sample size, which consists of 87 respondents, is based on the number of populations because there are fewer than 100.

Purposive and non-probability sampling is the sampling strategy used in this investigation. Not every population or component has an equal chance of being chosen as a sample when non-probability sampling is employed (Sugiyono, 2019). According to Nursalam (2008), the purposive sampling methodology is a way to choose specific samples based on community goals or research issues. Data analysis employing descriptive and inductive methodologies includes Smart PLS 3.9 analysis to uncover the suggested hypothesis.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Instrument Test

Below is an overview of the remaining items:

Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Convergent Validity

The results are shown in the following.

	Satisfaction	Skills	Performance	Experience
X1.1		0,823		
X1.2		0,946		
X1.3		0,903		
X1.4		0,913		
X1.5		0,917		
X2.1				0,954
X2.2				0,945
X2.3				0,879
X2.4				0,956
X2.5				0,940
Y1			0,823	
Y2			0,922	
Y3			0,828	
Y4			0,806	
Z1	0,920			
Z2	0,942			
Z3	0,824			
Z4	0,891			

All four of the variables are suitable for an exploratory investigation, as shown by the findings with scores greater than 0.6.

Discriminant Validity

The discriminant validity metric used in cross-loading and the average variance extracted (AVE) value are as follows:

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Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Satisfaction	0.802
Skills	0.813
Performance	0.715
Experience	0.874

It is known that the results are higher than 0.5. This indicates that all the study variable indicator instruments have been deemed legitimate.

Composite Reliability

The following displays the composite reliability results:

Variable	Composite Reliability
Satisfaction	0.942
Skills	0.956
Performance	0.909
Experience	0.972

Every variable under investigation has a reliability score higher than 0.7 based on the composite reliability test. This demonstrates the trustworthiness of the results.

Cronbach's Alpha

As shown below, the reliability test takes advantage of composite reliability:

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Satisfaction	0.917
Skills	0.943
Performance	0.867
Experience	0.964

According to the Cronbach's alpha reliability test, every variable is higher than 0.7, indicating the results are trustworthy.

Structural Analysis Model (Inner Model)

Goodness of Fit Analysis

Model	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Satisfaction	0,210	0,196
Performance	0,459	0,444

The information demonstrates that the skills and experience factors have a 0.196, or 19.6%, impact on satisfaction and a 0.444, or 44.4%, impact on performance.

Testing using Q-squared with computations:

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$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - [(1-R21) \times (1-R22)] \\
 &= 1 - [(1-0,196) \times (1-0,444)] \\
 &= 1 - (0,804 \times 0,556) \\
 &= 1 - 0,447 \\
 &= 0,553
 \end{aligned}$$

The model is useful since the result is 0.553, or 55.3%, while other factors can affect the dependent variable by up to 44.7%.

Normed Fit Index Model (NFI) Analysis Results

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.081	0.081
d_ ULS	1.114	1.114
d_ G	2.816	2.816
Chi-Square	1090.908	1090.908
NFI	0.632	0.632

The analysis's findings indicate that the NFI value is more than 0.1. Therefore, more tests can be conducted since this analysis model is viable.

Hypothesis Testing

Path Coefficients

Model	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Satisfaction → Performance	0,420	6,371	0,000
Skills → Satisfaction	0,347	4,338	0,000
Skills → Performance	0,196	2,794	0,005
Experience → Satisfaction	0,291	3,559	0,000
Experience → Performance	0,319	4,914	0,000

With a score of 6.371, the results demonstrate that the satisfaction variable has the biggest impact on performance. Following that, the experience variable has the second-largest impact on performance, with a value of 4.914. The third-largest influence on the satisfaction score of 4.338 is the skill variable. The fourth-largest influence on the satisfaction score of 3.559 is the experience variable. The skill variable has the fifth-largest impact on the performance of 2.794.

Indirect Effect Analysis Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Skills -> Satisfaction -> Performance	0,146	0,151	0,046	3,173	0,002
Experience -> Satisfaction -> Performance	0,122	0,127	0,046	2,678	0,008

The findings indicate that skills on performance through satisfaction can be acknowledged, with the t-value being 3.173 and the p-value being 0.002. Furthermore, a p-value of 0.008 < 0.05 and a t-value of 2.678 show that performance through satisfaction can be accepted.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SKILLS AND SATISFACTION

The impact of skills on satisfaction is substantial. These findings demonstrate that job satisfaction increases with skill level. To fulfill the company's aim, good talents must be matched with facilities and conditions to give employees job satisfaction. The more skilled an employee is, the more satisfied he will be with his job.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EXPERIENCE AND SATISFACTION

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Satisfaction is greatly impacted by experience. This finding indicates that workers with a lot of experience will do a fantastic job. Simultaneously, the terms or desires can fulfill the company's obligations, and seasoned workers will develop their competence areas.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SKILLS AND PERFORMANCE

Performance is significantly impacted by skills. According to these results, workers that possess more talents perform better. For employees to keep improving the firm's performance, the company should encourage their capabilities.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EXPERIENCE AND PERFORMANCE

Performance is significantly impacted by experience. According to these findings, people's knowledge, abilities, and attitudes relate to their activity. A person will eventually receive compensation for their aptitude and proficiency in completing and mastering the assigned duties. Employees with more work experience will find it easier to finish tasks, and their experience will impact their production ability to finish tasks and deliver quality work.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SATISFACTION AND PERFORMANCE

Performance is significantly impacted by satisfaction. These findings demonstrate that when workers express and are happy with their jobs, they are likelier to perform at their best and help the business reach its goals. Job satisfaction also helps the business increase revenue by boosting employee performance.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SKILLS AND PERFORMANCE MEDIATED WITH SATISFACTION

Performance that is mediated by satisfaction is significantly impacted by skills. According to these findings, job satisfaction may act as a moderator in the relation between satisfaction and skills. Work skills are crucial for a profession because they are required to help and finish the assigned tasks. Employee job satisfaction increases with their ability to do their work, leading to good performance that meets expectations.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EXPERIENCE AND PERFORMANCE MEDIATED WITH SATISFACTION

Experience significantly influences performance, which is mediated by satisfaction. These results imply that job satisfaction may mediate the association between work experience and performance. A person with experience may comprehend the responsibilities assigned and perform them effectively. Employees must possess good knowledge, including the ability to comprehend and apply information to job obligations because they undoubtedly have good experience.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The results indicate that first, skills significantly impact satisfaction. Second, satisfaction is significantly impacted by experience. Third, performance is significantly impacted by skills. Fourth, performance is significantly impacted by experience. Fifth, performance is significantly impacted by satisfaction. Sixth, performance mediated by satisfaction is significantly impacted by skills. Seventh: Performance mediated by satisfaction is significantly impacted by experience.

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